

DETERMINATION OF INFANT MILK INTAKE AND MOTHER'S BODY COMPOSITION IN BREASTFEEDING MOTHERS FROM ILE-IFE, USING STABLE ISOTOPE TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Infant milk intake and maternal body composition have been determined in 20 baby-mother pairs from Ile-Ife using the 'gold standard' technique for such measurements – the deuterium-dose-to-mother technique, currently being promoted by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), Vienna. Thirty milligram of sterile deuterium oxide was orally administered to each mother; and saliva samples were obtained from both mother and baby over a two-week period on days 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 13, and 14 following the dose. Deuterium enrichment in saliva was determined using Fourier-Transform Infra Red (FTIR) spectrometry. The transfer of deuterium from mother to baby through milk intake was modeled by a multi-exponential function, and the simultaneous solution of this function with the mono-exponential decay of deuterium from mother body pool was achieved using the SOLVER function in Microsoft Excel environment though a customized Spreadsheet supplied by the IAEA. Average milk intake over two weeks in the babies ranged from 387 to 1045 g/day. The average (\pm standard deviation) body mass, lean body mass, and body fat for the mothers were 53.7 ± 10.9 kg, 37.9 ± 7.01 kg, and 18.03 ± 9.87 kg respectively. There was a significant inverse correlation ($p < 0.02$) between milk intake in babies and the percentage body fat of mothers. This could imply that babies from women with low body fat need to consume larger quantities of milk to be satiated. Water intake from other sources apart from human milk (reflecting exclusiveness of breastfeeding in these babies) ranged from nil to 420g/day in the same period. These figures not only provide accurate data on these important nutrition parameters, but they could be used together with other figures to determine levels of nutrients and pollutants transferred to babies both through breast milk and non-breast milk sources.

Keywords: Human milk intake. Stable Isotopes

INTRODUCTION

Breastfeeding is a way of providing ideal food for the healthy growth and development of infants; as well as an integral part of the reproductive process. Because breastfeeding has many advantages for the child and mother (Oddy *et al.*, 2002; Horta *et al.*, 2007), the World Health Organization and many governments and professional associations recommend that infants

should be breastfed exclusively for the first six months of life. To meet their subsequent nutritional requirements thereafter, infants should receive nutritionally adequate and safe complementary foods while breastfeeding continues for up to 2 years of age or beyond (WHO, 2003).

Exclusive breastfeeding as defined by WHO (2008) is when an infant receives only breast milk and no other liquids or solids, with the exception of oral rehydration solutions, drops or syrups consisting of vitamins, mineral supplements or medicine. It has been estimated that the universal adoption of this practice (exclusive breastfeeding for six months) with continued partial breast feeding for a further six months could prevent 13% of childhood mortality under five years of age (Jones *et al.*, 2003). Unfortunately, in many settings, the rates of exclusive breastfeeding are low and linked with early introduction of complementary foods (Bhandari *et al.*, 2008).

Human milk is a complex living, biological fluid. It provides a diverse array of bioactive substances to the developing infant during critical periods of brain, immune, and gut development. It contains just the right amount of nutrients in the right proportion for the infant and cannot be duplicated by any laboratory formula. It is gently processed through the infants' digestive system so that these important nutrients are easily absorbed. To promote healthy growth, human milk changes in volume and composition according to the time of the day, nursing frequency, and the age of the baby (Anderson, 1984; Oddy *et al.*, 2002). The profound importance of human milk in optimizing neonatal health and improving child survival is becoming increasingly more apparent (Chung *et al.*, 2007; Bhutta *et al.*, 2008). Human milk intake measurement and its importance in determining energy and nutrients requirement by babies has been discussed both at national and international levels. (FAO, 2001; Ijarotimi and Ogunsemore, 2006; Ijarotimi, 2010).

One of the significant missing links in the knowledge regarding infant nutrition and health is quality data on feeding practices, i.e., data on breastfeeding duration and quantitative measures of milk intake and the time of introduction of complementary foods during the first two years of life. The lack of information on infant feeding practices is, at least partly, due to the difficulties involved in measuring intake of human milk. By conventional technique, infants are weighed before and after each feed, often referred to as "test weighing". It is assumed that the increase in the baby's mass (in grams) after feeding shows the amount (in millilitres) of milk consumed by the infants (Scanlon *et al.*, 2002). This technique is obviously time consuming, imprecise, prone to error, disturbs the normal feeding pattern, and special measures are required to assess night time feeding sessions (Imong *et al.*, 1989). By using a stable isotope technique, these practical problems can be overcome as the normal feeding pattern is not disrupted and the total volume of human milk, consumed by the baby over a period of 14 days, is measured. Furthermore, the stable isotope technique is relatively easy. Unlike alternative methods, such as test weighing and use of flow meter, the stable isotope technique does not need an observer to be present at the time of feeding.

The accuracy, cheapness and ready availability of deuterium oxide ($^2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) has led to its extensive use in measuring body composition (Westerterp *et al.*, 1995) and in the estimation of infants' human milk intake (Coward *et al.*, 1982; Fjeld *et al.*, 1988). It is non-invasive as the dose of deuterium oxide is consumed orally by the mother and only samples of urine or saliva

are collected for analyses. The enrichment of deuterium in body water is measured by Isotope Ratio Mass Spectrometry (IRMS) or Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometry (FTIR). At the same time, information about whether the infant has consumed water from other sources than human milk (indicating intake of complementary foods and/or fluids), can be obtained. So also can the mother's total body water content be accurately assessed.

The measurement of body composition provides an objective means of nutritional status. The most common approach in body composition assessment is to utilize the two-compartment model, dividing body mass into body fat mass (FM) and fat free mass (FFM). Despite the large number of body composition measurement techniques available, only three primary techniques are widely recognized: densitometry, elemental analysis, and total body water (TBW) measurement.

The total body water (TBW) includes both intra-cellular and extra-cellular fluids. It comprises 73.2% of the FFM (IAEA, 2009). When combined with knowledge of FFM hydration, analysis of TBW leads to accurate FFM estimates. Body fat is then calculated as the difference between body mass and FFM. TBW can best be measured with accuracy using isotope dilution technique (Schoeller *et al.*, 1980; Halliday and Miller, 1977). TBW analysis has overcome past difficulties as stable isotope dilution (using either ^2H or ^{18}O) can be applied with greater safety, precision and accuracy than using radioisotopes (^3H). TBW measurement, using stable isotope labels, is clearly the most appropriate primary method of body composition analysis suitable for field use. In this study, the state-of-the-art stable isotope dilution method has been used to determine human milk intake and intake of water from sources other than human milk by babies, and mothers' body composition using the deuterium dose-to-the-mother method of Coward *et al.* (1982).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of Subjects

Thirty nursing mother-baby pairs were recruited into the study from the Primary Health Centre, Enuwa, Ile-Ife, Osun State. The data obtained for nine mother-baby pairs could not be satisfactorily described by the model because some of the participants could not complete the two week study period. This reduced the size of the data set to twenty one. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital Complex (OAUTHC). The mothers gave their voluntary consent to take part in the study after being adequately informed of its purpose, requirements, and procedures. The necessary information such as mother's ID, study date, mother's mass (kg), mother's height (m), dose mass (g), dose number, time of baseline sampling, time of dose consumption, date and time of saliva sampling on days 1, 2, 3, 4, 13 and 14 post-dose; baby's mass and babies length were recorded.

Determination of Body Mass

Mothers were asked to empty their bladder (and if possible bowels) before they were weighed to the nearest 0.1kg using an electronic scale. Mothers were weighed in light clothing. The body masses of the mothers were measured prior to the ingestion of the deuterium dose (baseline) and again on day 14 to ensure that it has not changed substantially. The babies were weighed to the nearest 0.01kg without clothes using an electronic scale. As for the mothers, babies' masses were measured both at the baseline and on day 14.

Deuterium Dose Preparation and Storage

The standardized dose of deuterium for assessing human milk intake using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrometer is 30g for all adult body masses. Thirty gram of deuterium doses (99.8 at.% ^2H) was weighed with an electronic weighing balance accurate to 0.1mg. Lids were removed from some 100ml bottles and the bottles were weighed. Thirty milliliters of $^2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was poured into each of the weighed bottles. The bottles plus $^2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were weighed. The same measuring cylinder was used for all doses prepared in a single session, since it was only used for highly enriched deuterium oxide. The measuring cylinder was not washed with water between doses to prevent it from being contaminated with water which will lead to an error in the amount of $^2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ given to the mothers.

Doses were prepared in a clean environment. All equipment (dose bottles and measuring cylinders used) for preparing the doses were completely dry to avoid contamination by water. Dose bottles were screw-capped and leak proof to avoid loss during storage and contamination by moisture from the environment. Doses were prepared in batches based on the number of subjects available and stored in a refrigerator until required. Samples of dose of $^2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and of local water used for the dose preparation, were kept for analysis.

Dose Administration

Assessment of human milk ingested by the infants was determined by the deuterium oxide dose-to-mother technique using a standardized procedure (IAEA, 2010). Baseline saliva samples were obtained from the mother and the baby before the dose was administered to the mother. The dose bottles were inverted to mix any condensation in the cap into the bulk of the liquid to avoid errors associated with dose-fractionation. The mother ingested the doses by sipping slowly using a straw. In order to ensure that no deuterium labeled water was left in the bottle, 50ml of drinking water was added to the dose bottle and the mothers were asked to drink it through the same straw.

Saliva Sampling

Saliva Sampling for Mothers

Each mother was asked to expectorate into a pre-labelled storage vial prior to the administration of the dose. After the dose had been administered to the mother, the post-dose saliva samples were obtained by asking each mother to expectorate into other pre-labelled storage vials. Post-dose saliva samples were collected on days 1, 2, 3, 4, 13, and 14. A minimum 2 ml of saliva sample was obtained from each subject. Saliva samples collected by direct expectoration contain particulate matter. The saliva samples were therefore centrifuged at the Medical Microbiology Laboratory of the College of Health Sciences, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, in order to separate the particles from the saliva. A clean glove was used for each participant. The date and time of sample collection were recorded on the study information sheet.

Saliva Sampling for Babies

Before the saliva samples were collected from the babies, it was ensured that the babies had not been breastfed for at least 15 minutes. With a clean glove, pre-sterilized cotton wool swab was moved round the baby's mouth until the cotton wool was sodden. The cotton wool was removed from the swab and placed in the body of a (5 ml) syringe. The syringe plunger was used to extract saliva from the sodden cotton wool into a labelled storage vial. The process was repeated several times until at least 2 ml of saliva was obtained. The process required care and patience and it took several minutes per baby.

Storage and Analyses of Saliva Samples

The mother's and the baby's post-dose saliva samples were placed in the same bag. The mother's and the baby's baseline samples were placed in a separate bag. Deuterium doses and saliva samples were stored in different places to avoid microbial contamination. Saliva samples were stored in a fridge to minimize bacterial growth until it was analysed. Mothers' Saliva samples were completely thawed and centrifuged at 1000 g for 10 minutes and the supernatant was kept at -20 °C until it was analysed.

Determination of Deuterium Enrichment in Saliva Samples

Deuterium enrichment in saliva was determined using Fourier-Transform Infra Red spectrometry at the Centre for Energy Research and Development of the Obafemi Awolowo University, with deuterium being determined in the FTIR spectra in the range 1800 – 2800 cm^{-1} . The special CaF_2 cell in which the saliva samples were presented to the spectrometer was supplied by the Central Science Laboratory of the Obafemi Awolowo University. The pre and post-dose samples were loaded into the spectrometer and automatically positioned in the light beam in order to minimize any interference due to the absorption of CO_2 in the sample chamber. The deuterium enrichment in the saliva sample of each mother and the baby was obtained by subtracting post-dose spectrum from the baseline spectrum peak using Omnic software. An

algorithm (ISOTOPE.EXE), developed by the Medical Research Council Collaborative Centre for Human Nutrition (MRC-HNR), Cambridge, UK, was used to both simplify as well as enhance the accuracy of the calculation of the deuterium enrichment (IAEA, 2010). This gives the enrichment in each of the samples in parts per million (ppm).

Procedures and Algorithms for Determination of Human Milk Intake and Intake of Water From Sources Other Than Human Milk

Calculation of human milk intake and intake of water from sources other than human milk is based on two compartment model. Intake of breast milk and water from non-milk sources was calculated by fitting the isotopic (tracer) data to a model for water (tracee) turnover in the mothers and infants and the transfer of milk from mother to the baby (Coward *et al.*, 1982)

In the two compartment model (depicted in Figure 1), the mother's body water (V_m) is the first compartment and the baby's body water (V_b) is the second compartment. These two compartments are connected by the flow of milk from the mother to the baby (F_{bm}). In a steady state model, the total water input is equal to the total water output. As is the convention in compartmental models, the first subscript in F_{bm} indicates where the flow goes to while the second indicates where the flow is from. Flows are also shown from the outside (o) to the mother (F_{mo}), i.e. the water she drinks, and from the mother to the outside, i.e. the water she loses from her body in urine, faeces, sweat and breath. Similarly, F_{bo} is the flow from the outside to the baby, i.e. water intake by the baby from sources other than human milk. The final flow is from the baby to the outside, F_{ob} , i.e. the water lost from the baby's body in urine, faeces, sweat, saliva and breath. In the Figure 1, F signifies the flow of water.

Figure 1: Two compartment steady state model of water flow in a mother-baby pair. F=flow; m= mother; b= baby; o= outside; v= volume.

The two compartment steady state model is based on a number of assumptions. Where these assumptions do not hold true, an adjustment is included in the calculations. These assumptions and the adjustment made to ensure their validity are shown on Table 1

Table 1: Calculations and Assumptions Used For Calculating Breast Milk Intake

PARAMETER	CALCULATION	ORIGIN
Breast milk intake (M)	$M = F_{bm} / 0.871$	Breast milk is 87.1% water (Holland <i>et al.</i> , 1991)
Total water input derived from breast milk (F_m)	$F_m = F_{bm} + 0.09M$	The water in breast milk and the water of oxidation of milk solids. These give about 9 g water/100 g breast milk.
Water gained in growth during the experimental period (F_g)	$F_g = (V_{b,14day} - V_{b,0day}) / 14$	Calculated from the changes in V_b
Total water output from the baby (F_{ob})	$F_{ob} = F_{bb} / 0.9915$	A correction for isotopic fractionation assuming that 15% of the infants' water losses were fractionated
Non oral water intake in the infant (F_a)	$F_a = 0.063M$	Water exchange between atmospheric and mainly alveolar water is estimated as 6.3% of milk intake (Wells & Davies, 1995)
Nonmilk oral (supplement) water intake (F_s)	$F_s = F_{ob} - F_m - F_a + F_g$	Water input ($F_s + F_m + F_a$) equals water output plus water from growth ($F_{ob} + F_g$)

Adapted from: Holland *et al.*, 1991; Wells and Davies, 1995

Implementation of the Procedures for Determining Human Milk Intake (M) and Intake of Water from Sources other than Human Milk (F_s) in the Baby

The data obtained from ISOTOPE.EXE is fed into a Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet supplied by the IAEA and pre-programmed for the calculation of the milk intake according to equations 1 and 2 below (IAEA 2010):

For the mother

$$E_{m(t)} = E_{m(0)} e^{-K_{mm}t} \quad (1)$$

and for the baby

$$E_{b(t)} = E_{m(0)} \left(\frac{F_{bm}}{V_b} \right) \left(\frac{e^{k_{mm}t} - e^{\left(\frac{F_{bb}}{V_b}\right)t}}{\left(\frac{F_{bb}}{V_b}\right) - k_{mm}} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where, $\frac{F_{bb}}{V_b} = k_{bb}$

and

$E_{m(t)}$ is the deuterium enrichment in the mother's body water at time t, in mg/kg or ppm;

t is the time since the dose was taken, i.e. time post-dose in days;

$E_{m(0)}$ is the deuterium enrichment in the mother's body water at time zero mg/kg (ppm), i.e. the y intercept of the isotope elimination curve (log/linear plot of enrichment of ^2H in body water versus time).

k_{mm} is the fractional water turnover in the mother (kg/d), i.e. the gradient of the isotope elimination curve.

$E_{b(t)}$ is the deuterium enrichment in the baby's body water at time, t, in mg/kg (ppm);

F_{bm} is the transfer of water from the mother to the baby via human milk (kg/d);

V_b is the baby's total ^2H distribution space (kg). V_b is assumed to change linearly with initial and final values determined from the baby's mass (W, kg).

F_{bb} is the total water loss in the baby (kg/d).

k_{bb} is the gradient of the baby's isotope elimination curve.

The value of ^2H enrichment obtained from the analysis of samples collected from mother and her breastfed infant over a 14 days period was subtracted from the pre dose values. The two equations were simultaneously solved, by iteration, using the 'Solver' function in Microsoft Excel to minimise the sum of the squares of the differences between observed and fitted values for mother and baby data combined. Solver uses non-linear regression to determine by iteration, the value of the constants that gave the line of best fit through the data. This procedure requires initial estimates for the unknown parameters ($E_{m(0)}$, F_{bm} , k_{mm} and F_{bb}) and, subsequently, refines them to converge on best fit values. V_b , total body water of the baby, was calculated from Friis- Hansen formula for children less than 1 year of age which is as follows:

$$V_b = 0.84W^{0.82}$$

where W is the body mass (kg) and V_b is the volume (litre).

F_{bm} is obtained by multiplying F_{bm}/V_b by an estimate of V_b , since F_{bm} represents only the free water in milk and does not include water from the oxidation of milk solids.

Milk-intake/day (M) is obtained from the expression below by assuming that milk is 87.1% water.

$$M = F_{bm}/0.87 \text{ kg/day.}$$

Measured human milk intake is often expressed in g/d. Other parameters can also be calculated from the data available from the above methodology, e.g, estimates of breast milk output, maternal body composition (total lean body mass and total fat) and estimates of non-milk water intake (F_{bo}). The baby's total intake of water includes water from the oxidation of milk solids (protein, fat and carbohydrate) and water from sources other than human milk. The total water input derived from human milk is F_m . Calculation of F_s (nonmilk oral water intake) assumes that water input equals water output.

$$\text{Water input} = (F_m + F_a + F_s)$$

Water input equals water output plus water from growth ($F_{ob} + F_g$); therefore:

$$F_s = F_{ob} + F_g - F_m - F_a$$

The flow of water from the mother to the baby (F_{bm}) represents free water in milk and does not include water from the oxidation of milk solids (protein, fat and carbohydrate): Human milk is assumed to contain 87.1% water, 1.3% protein, 4.1% fat and 7.2% carbohydrate (Holland *et al.*, 1991). The yield of water from 1 g of protein is 0.41 g, from 1 g of fat is 1.07 g and from 1 g of carbohydrate 0.55 g. Therefore, oxidation of milk solids gives about 9 g of water per 100 g of human milk. Total water input to the baby derived from human milk (F_m) is given by:

$$F_m = F_{bm} + 0.09M$$

Procedure and Algorithm for Determination of Maternal Body Composition

The mothers' total body water (TBW, kg) was calculated using the back-extrapolation technique (IAEA, 2010). Fat free mass (FFM, kg) was determined from TBW using a non-aqueous exchange factor of 1.041. Fat mass (kg) was calculated as the difference between the mother's body mass (kg) and FFM (kg). Zero time enrichment ($E_{m(0)}$, ppm) was estimated as the intercept of the fitted maternal isotopic disappearance curve. V_D must be corrected for non-aqueous isotopic exchange. Non- aqueous isotopic exchange for deuterium is 4.1 % of the pool space. The pool size (V_D) was calculated thus:

$$(V_D) = \frac{\text{Deuterium dose given to the mother (g)}}{E_{m(0)}} \times 100$$

TBW is therefore calculated by dividing V_D by 1.041

$$\text{TBW} = \frac{V_D \text{ (kg)}}{1.041}$$

FFM in adult is assumed to be 73.2% water. Thus:

$$\text{FFM (kg)} = \frac{\text{TBW (kg)}}{0.732}$$

FM is calculated as the difference between FFM and body mass

$$FM(kg) = \text{body mass (kg)} - \text{FFM (kg)}$$

$$FM (\%) = \frac{FM (kg)}{\text{Body mass (kg)}} \times 100$$

RESULTS

The calibration curve plotting measured enrichment against calculated enrichment (mg/kg) is shown in Figure 2. The r^2 value of 0.9986 indicate sufficient accuracy of our experimental set-up.

Typical milk intake curves obtained for each mother-baby pair are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4 for an exclusively-breastfed baby and partially-breastfed baby respectively. The difference in the amount of deuterium transferred to the baby and that in the mother is obvious. For an exclusively breastfed baby, when the enrichment curves of the mother and child are plotted on the same graph, as shown in Figure 3, the mother's curve crosses that of the child at its maximum value. For a child who is fed complementary foods alongside breast milk, the maximum of the child's curve falls below the mother's curve, as shown in Figure 4. The relative heights of the child's and mother's curves at this time represent the fraction of feeding due to breast milk. The extracted values of the relevant parameters for all 20 mother-baby pairs are shown in Table 2.

The results obtained for mother 6, 9, 11, 14 and 16 with negative percent body fat and negative fat free mass are in error. This could be as a result of the error encountered while filling the cell or due to some other errors in the field. They were therefore not used in the final analysis.

The average maternal age at the time of measurement was 27.1 (range 19-35) years. The average maternal body mass was 53.7 ± 10.9 kg. The infants had an average age of 104 ± 71.1 days. At the beginning of the study period, the infants had average body mass 5.64 ± 1.12 kg. The average body mass increase during the two weeks study period was 0.29 ± 0.34 kg. Three of the twenty one infants lost weight during the study period. The results are quoted as mean \pm standard deviation.

From the isotope data, the maternal lean body mass (FFM) was 37.9 ± 7.01 kg and the mean maternal body fat was 18.03 ± 9.87 kg. The average maternal water turnover of the mothers was 0.80 ± 0.29 kg/day. Water consumed orally other than breast milk ranged from -602 to 847 g/day.

Correlation coefficients

Some of the observed Interesting/Key Correlations are:

Baby's MUAC vs Mother's BMI $r = 0.872$

Milk Intake vs % Fat of Mother $r = -0.567$ ($p < 0.02$)

Water Output vs Non-oral water intake $r = 0.996$

Water Output vs Non-milk intake $r = 0.747$

Weight gained by babies vs Net intake of fluids $r = 0.964$.

DISCUSSION

Non-milk (oral) intake of the infants positively correlated with age ($r = 0.92$, $p = 0.30$). A similar study conducted in Texas in the United States of America reported that non-milk oral intake does not increase with age (Bandara *et al.*, 2014). This might be a reflective of the cultural differences. The deuterium oxide dose-to-mother technique categorizes the infants as exclusively breastfed if the non-milk oral intake is less than 25 g/day (Haisma *et al.*, 2003, Moore *et al.*, 2007). In the current study, only five out of the sixteen infants (31%) were found to have non-milk oral intake to be less than 25 g/day.

The average percentage fat mass (%FM) in this study was $31.2 \pm 14.8\%$. In 2003, Haisma *et al.*, reported the %FM of the Brazilian mothers at 4 months of lactation to be $24.7 \pm 3.9\%$. Galpin *et al.*, 2007 also reported that the %FM of Malawi mothers at 6-9 months of lactation ranged from 22% to 25%. TBW of the mothers in the present study was 32.1 ± 9.3 kg. In another study, TBW was found to range between 27.2 ± 2.9 kg and 28.5 ± 1.9 kg in well-nourished Mexican mothers at 4-6 months of lactation (Butte *et al.*, 1992)

There was a negative correlation between milk intake and mothers age ($p = -0.76$) %FM ($p = -0.01$), FFM ($p = -0.03$) and mothers body mass ($p = -0.04$). Hytten, (1954) reported that the amount of functional tissues in the breast determines the level of milk yield. The functional tissues may decrease with age. He therefore suggested that the capacity to lactate is greatest before age 20 and reduces thereafter.

Of the sixteen subjects analysed, nine are females and seven are males. The average human milk intake for sixteen infants (nine females and seven males) whose ages are less than six months reported by Bandara *et al.*, (2014) are 1350 ± 170 g/day and 1110 ± 290 g/day respectively. The average value for the human milk intake of nine females and seven males obtained in the current study are 876 ± 327 g/day and 786 ± 337 g/day respectively.

In this study, the value of human milk intake obtained is 878 ± 336 g/day. Dewey *et al.*, 1991 reported that the mean human milk intake of EBF (exclusively breastfed) infants of the well-

nourished mothers is 700 ± 800 g/day during the first five months of life. However, according to Rattigan *et al.* (1981), the maximum amount of milk production by a lactating mother ranges between 721 and 927 g/day. In the current study, human milk intake was 710 ± 193 g/day, 834 ± 324 g/day and 1150 ± 356 g/day for infants < 2 months, 2 to < 4 months and 4 to 6 months of age respectively. The results obtained in this study is higher than the previously reported values.

Estimating Maternal Body Composition and Human Milk Intake

The comparison of human milk intake by deuterium oxide-dose-to-the-mother technique across different countries is summarized in Table 3. Human milk intake obtained from this study (853 ± 325 g/day) is comparable with those reported in the Table. It has been shown that lactation performance is robust against moderate maternal undernourishment, although it will inevitably be compromised by very low energy intakes (Prentice *et al.*, 1981, Whitehead *et al.*, 1981). An inverse relationship between breast milk output and maternal body fat has been previously reported (Agampodi *et al.*, 2007 (Brazil), Bandara *et al.*, 2014 (Mexico), Moore *et al.*, 2007 (Malawi)).

The results obtained from this study, ($p = -0.04$), agrees with these observations. This indicates that high levels of maternal body fat reduce human milk production and increase the use of other foods. The introduction of complementary food with reduction in breastfeeding reduces the energy cost to the mother, allowing her to increase weight. The mothers' body composition varies and it depends on factors such as weight gained before birth, level of physical activity, stage of lactation, the mother's nutritional status, cultural practices and food availability. It does not seem to be determined by ethnicity. (Butte and Hopkinson, 1998; Robinson, 1986)

As demonstrated by Nagy and Costa (1980) the most unpredictable and unavoidable source of error in the deuterium-oxide-dose-to-mother technique is the influx of unlabelled environmental water. Fjeld *et al.*, (1988) estimated that influx of environmental water could be up to as much as 32% of total water flux in infants exposed to an absolute humidity of 31.5 mg/l. It is difficult to estimate the actual climatic conditions to which an infant is exposed (especially in industrialized countries where air conditioners are mostly used). In this study, the estimate of environmental water influx was based on assumptions regarding respiratory rate, and that water intake by the baby is only by ingestion.

The 2013 Nigerian Demographic and Health Survey reports that although all babies (98%) are breastfed in Nigeria, (Victor, 2015). Only a minority of mothers (33%) achieves the WHO – recommended initiation within one hour of birth and only 17% continues to breastfeed exclusively for six months. There is a large range in early initiation of breastfeeding rates by states in Nigeria. The highest rates in Kogi (74%), Kwara (71%), Borno (68%), Abia (64%), Edo (55%) and the Federal Capital Territory (51%) and the lowest in Kebbi (8%), Zamfara (12%), Taraba (14%), Ebonyi (17%), Katsina (18%), and Lagos (20%). Victor (2015), reported that breastfeeding rates are highest in North Central and South South zones and lowest in North West and South West zones in Nigeria. Mothers that are educated and have a high income are more likely to breastfeed exclusively for six months. The stable isotope technique used in this method

is a more accurate method of determining levels of exclusively breastfeeding and it also gives an estimate of the intake of water from sources other than human milk

Mothers with a lower fraction of total body fat, had infants who consumed more milk. Perhaps these mothers with a lower fraction of body fat and poorer nutritional status were producing breast milk with a lower energy density, and thus their infants consumed more of this milk in an effort to meet their energy requirements. Previous work in Bangladesh concluded that mothers with a poorer nutritional status, produced breast milk with a lower fat and energy content (Brown *et al.*, 1986).

CONCLUSION

The deuterium dilution method has been applied to determine human milk intake and maternal body composition in Nigerian subjects. Mothers were recruited from the Primary Health centre, Enuwa, Ile-Ife. Thus, the study population can be reflective of the mothers who are more concerned about the nutrition and well-being of their infants. The volume of milk consumed by infants in the first six months of life has traditionally been set as 850 ml/day (876 g/day) (WHO, 2008). Milk intakes of some babies that are within this age bracket are lower than this value. This shows that the breast milk intake the babies consume may not be adequate to facilitate proper growth. About 31% (5 out of 16) breastfeeding mothers exclusively breastfed in this study. Insufficient breast milk secretion, working status and poor nutritional status may discourage some mothers in this study from practicing exclusive breast feeding. An inverse relationship was established for mother's body fat and baby's milk intake. This could imply that babies from women with low body fat need to consume larger quantities of milk to be satiated.

Maternal body composition and infant breast milk intakes determined in this study can be combined with other nutritional and environmental parameters to substantially enhance public health in Nigeria.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This Research is sponsored by the International Atomic Energy Agency, (IAEA) Vienna, through Research Contract NIR15828. The special CaF₂ cell used for FTIR analyses of saliva samples was supplied by the Central Science Laboratory of the Obafemi Awolowo University. Prof Aaron Aboderin gave access to the centrifuges at the Medical Microbiology Laboratory.

Table 2: Summary of the outputs of key parameters from the Spreadsheet for determination of breastmilk intake in subjects

ID	M- BMI	MUAC	M- Age	Parity	%Fat (id)	Milk intake	Water output	Non- oral intake	Non- milk intake	Sq root MSE	M- Mass	Baby's Mass Day 1 (kg)	Baby's Mass Day 14 (kg)	Baby's Mass Gain (kg)	Baby's Net fluid Intake (kg)	Baby's Age (months)
1	22.1	24.5	28	3	26.9	826	874	56	43	88.66	57.4	3.57	4.07	0.5	51	6
2	22.1	26	35	3	28.3	676	575	37	-104	128.01	55.9	3.71	3.93	0.22	34	1.5
3	27.5	24	21	1	37.2	854	1054	67	182	96.9	57	6.24	6.69	0.45	49	2.3
4	23.3	23.5	31	3	27.7	610	1359	86	689	90.699	45	6.37	6.42	0.05	26	1
5	28	29.1	30	3	41.3	457	782	51	313	59.52	70	4.47	5.06	0.59	39	1.3
6	21.7	25.7	29	4	24.7	790	802	51	-5	28.78	45	5.34	5.4	0.06	34	2.8
7	20	23	23	1	29.7	720	1001	60	194	96	42	6.16	4.65	-1.51	-27	5
8	23.3	24.8	30	3	27.3	997	961	61	-51	47.84	59	6	6.2	0.2	46	2.67
9	21.5	26.5	32	5	13.5	981	909	58	-76	58.5	49	4.68	5.12	0.44	54	1.3
10	26.3	30.5	27	3	27.8	521	578	37	54	97.19	56	3.11	3.47	0.36	34	2.5
11	35.7	36	30	3	35	980	916	58	-72	58.87	89	6.9	7.3	0.4	50	4
12	23.1	24	26	2	27.1	884	1347	85	420	99.58	50	5.75	5.97	0.22	42	5.8
13	23.5	27.5	20	1	14.8	1045	1481	94	397	56.49	55	6.46	6.73	0.27	55	5.3
14	23.8	24	24	3	42.4	387	347	23	-27	87.02	61	6.05	6.12	0.07	36	4.5
15	20.9	25.5	32	4	34.6	585	934	60	329	101.38	55.4	5.3	5.75	0.45	40	3
16	24.5	24.5	22	2	49.3	754	527	34	-223	61.69	49	4.72	4.93	0.21	38	2
17	37.8	36.5	21	3	49.7	515	1164	74	611	60.13	98	7.05	7.51	0.46	36	9.7
18	26.2	25.6	19	1	35.5	886	981	68	153	69.97	63	3.34	5.77	2.43	126	2
19 (Z)			31		41.5	1399	3604	229	2065	60.01	62	5.1	6	0.9	89	4.3
20 (Z)			33		40	590	568	39	8	101.16	53	3.02	4.1	1.08	69	1.5

Figure 2: FTIR calibration curve used in this study.

^2H Kinetics

Figure 3: A Typical plot showing the declining curve of deuterium concentration in the saliva of mother 2 (filled triangle) and enrichment curve in the saliva of baby 2 (filled circle) for an EXCLUSIVELY BREASTFED baby.

^2H Kinetics

Figure 4: A typical plot showing the declining curve of deuterium concentration in the saliva of mother 12 (filled triangle) and the enrichment curve in the saliva of baby 12 (filled circle) for a PARTIALLY-BREASTFED baby

Table 3 Comparison of milk intake measurements made using the dose-to-the-mother method in a number of settings. EBF (exclusively breastfed), PBF (partially breastfed).

Country	Maternal % body fat (kg)	Infant Age (months)	Feeding Pattern	Breast Milk Intake (g·day ⁻¹)
Bangladesh (Ettyang <i>et al.</i> , 2005)	---	3.5	EBF	911 ± 168
Brazil (Agampodi <i>et al.</i> , 2007)	34 ± 6	4	EBF	881
Ethiopia (Albernaz <i>et al.</i> , 2003)	27 ± 6	1.5	EBF	880 ± 120
Kenya (Haisma <i>et al.</i> , 2003)	17 ± 6	2-4	EBF	569 ± 23
	22 ± 6	5	EBF	955 ± 189
Malawi (Moore <i>et al.</i>)	21 ± 9	5.5	EBF	921 ± 185
	25 ± 7	5.5	EBF	839 ± 109
Mexico (Bandara <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	24 ± 6	4	EBF	885 ± 146
	23 ± 7	6	EBF	869 ± 150
Papua New Guinea (Butte <i>et al.</i> , 1991)	----	4-6	PBF	863 ± 157
This study	31±15	1-9	EBF AND PBF	853±325

REFERENCES

- Agampodi S.B., Agampodi T.C., Kankanamge U. and Piyaseeli D., (2007). Breastfeeding practices in a public health field practice area in Sri Lanka: a survival analysis. *Int Breastfeed Journal* ; 2:13
- Albernaz E., Victora G.C., Haisma H., Wright A., and Coward W.A. (2003). Lactation counseling increases breast-feeding duration but not breast milk intake as measured by isotopic methods. *J Nutr*;133:205–10
- Anderson G.H. (1984). The effect of prematurity on milk composition and its physiological basis. *Fed Proc*; 43: 24-38
- Bandara T., Hettiarachi M., Liyanage C., and Amarasena S. (2014). Current infant feeding practices and impact on growth in babies during the second half of infancy. *J Hum Nutr Diet*. Epub ahead of print; DOI:10.1111/jhn.12253.

- Bhandari N. Iqbal K. and Mohammed A.S. (2008). Mainstreaming nutrition into maternal and child health programmes: scaling up of exclusive breastfeeding, *Matern. Child Nutr.*(Suppl 1) 5-23
- Bhutta Z.A., Ahmed T., Black, R.E., Cousens S., Dewey K., Guigliani E., Haider B.A., Kirkwood B., Morris S.S., Sachdev H.P.S and Shekar M. (2008). What works? Interventions for maternal and child undernutrition and survival. *Lancet.*;371:417–40.
- Brown, K.H., Akhtar, N.A., Robertson, AD., and Ahmed, M.G. (1986). Lactational capacity of marginally nourished mothers: Relationships between maternal nutritional status and quantity and proximate composition of milk. *Pediatrics* 78: 909-919.
- Butte N.F., Wong W.W., Klein and Graza C. (1991). Measurement of milk intake: tracer-to-infant deuterium dilution method. *Br J Nutr*; 65: 3–14.
- Butte N., Villalpando S., Wong W.W., Flores-Huerta S., Hernandez Beltran M.D., Smith O.E. and Garza C. 1992. Human milk intake and growth faltering of rural Mesoamerican infants. *Am J Clin. Nutr*; 55: 1109–1116.
- Butte N.F. and Hopkinson J. M. (1998). Body composition changes during lactation are highly variable among women. *J Nutr*, 128(2):381S-385S
- Chung, M., Raman,G., Chew P., Ip S., Magula N., DeVine D., Trikalinos T., and Lau J. (2007). Breastfeeding and maternal and infant health outcomes in developed countries. In: Evidence report/technology assessment no 153. Rockville, MD: Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality
- Coward W.A., Cole T.J., Sawyer M.B., and Prentice A.M. (1982). Breast-milk intake measurement in mixed-fed infants by administration of deuterium oxide to their mothers. *Hum. Nutr. Clin. Nutr.*; 36: 141–148.
- Dewey K.G., Heinig M.J., Nommsen L.A. and Lonnerdal B. (1991). Maternal versus infant factors related to breast milk intake and residual milk volume: the DARLING study. *Pediatrics*. 87: 829-837.
- Ettyang G. A., Lichtenbelt W.D., Esamai F., Saris W.H. and Westerterp K.R. (2005). Assessment of Body Composition and Breast Milk Volume in Lactating Mothers in Pastoral Communities in Pokot, Kenya, Using Deuterium Oxide. *Annals of Nutrition and Metabolism*.49(2):110–117. doi:10.1159/000084744.
- FAO 2001. Human Energy Requirements. Report of a Joint FAO/WHO/UNU Expert Consultation Rome, 17–24 October 2001. *Food and Nutrition Reports Series No 1*. Available at <http://www.fao.org/3/a-y5686e.pdf> (Accessed 11-11-16)
- Fjeld C.R., Brown K.H. and Schoeller D.A. (1988): Validation of the deuterium oxide method for measuring average daily milk intake in infants. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 48: 671–679.
- Galpin L., Thakwalakwa C., Phuka J., Ashorn P., Maleta K., Wong W.W. and Manary M.J. (2007). Breast milk intake is not reduced more by the introduction of energy dense complementary food than by typical infant porridge. *J Nutr*;137:1828–1833.
- Haisma H., Coward W.A., Albernaz E., Visser G.H., Wells J.C., Wright A. and Victora C.G. (2003). Breast milk and energy intake in exclusively, predominantly, and partially breastfed infants. *Eur J Clin Nutr* ; 57:1633–1642.
- Halliday, D. and Miller, A.G. (1977). Precise measurement of total body water using trace quantities of deuterium oxide, *Biomed. Mass Spec.* 4(2) 82-87
- Holland B., Welch A.A., Unwin I.D., Buss D.H., Paul A.A. and Southgate D.A. (1991). The composition of foods, 5th Edition. Cambridge, UK: McChance and Widdowson.

- Horta B., Bahl R., Martines J. and Victora C. (2007). Evidence of the long-term effects of breastfeeding. Geneva: WHO; 2007.
- Hyttén F.E., (1954). Clinical and chemical studies in human lactation: VI. The functional capacity of the breast. *BMJ* 1954; April 17:912-5.
- Ijarotimi, O.S. 2010. Assessing exclusive breastfeeding practices, dietary intakes and body mass index (BMI) of nursing mothers in Ekiti State of Nigeria. *Nutr Res Pract.* 4(3): 222–228.
- Ijarotimi, O.S., Ogunsemore, M.T. 2006. Weaning foods and their impact on child-feeding practices among low-income Nigerian mothers. *Food Nutr Bull.* 27(4):327-334.
- Imong S.M., Jackson, Dorothy A., Wongsawasdi, Lumduan, Ruckphaophunt S., Tansuhaj, Antika, Chiowanich, Pien W., Drewett R.F., Baum J.D., Amatayakul, and Kosin. (1989) Predictors of Breast-Milk Intake in Rural Northern Thailand. *Journal of Pediatric Gastroenterology Nutrition.*;8(3):359–370.
- International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) (2009). Assessment of body composition and total energy expenditure in humans by stable isotope techniques. IAEA Human Health Series 3. Vienna: IAEA-
- International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), (2010). Human Health Series No.7. Stable isotope techniques to assess intake of human milk in breastfed infants. Vienna (Austria): IAEA.
- Jones G., Steketee R.W., Black R.E., Bhutta Z.A., Morris S.S. and Bellagio G., (2003). Child Survival Study, (2003). How Many Child Deaths Can We Prevent This Year? *Lancet*; 362(9377): 65–71. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(03)13811-1.
- Moore S.E., Prentice A.M., Coward W.A., Wright A., Frongillo E.A., Fulford A.J., Mander P., Persson L., Arifeen S.E. and Kabir I. (2007). Use of stable-isotope techniques to validate infant feeding practices reported by Bangladeshi women receiving breast feeding counseling. *Am J Clin Nutr*;85:1075–82.
- Nagy, K.A. and Costa, D.P. (1980). Water flux in animals: analysis of potential errors in the tritiated water method. *American Journal of Physiology*, 238, R454-R465.
- Oddy, W., Sly P.D., de Klerk N.H., Landau L.I., Kendall G.E., Holt P.G. (2002). The impact of breast milk on infant and child health. *Breastfeeding Rev*; 10(3):5-18
- Prentice A.M., Whitehead R.G., Roberts S.B. and Paul A.A., (1981) . Long-Term Energy-Balance in Child bearing Gambian Women. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition.*;34(12):2790–2799.
- Rattigan S., Ghisalberti A.V. and Hartmann P.E., (1981). Breast milk production in Australian women. *Br. J. Nutr.* 1981;45:243–9.
- Robinson, J. J., (1986). Changes in body composition during pregnancy and lactation. *Proc. Nutr. Soc.* 45, 71–80.
- Scanlon K.S., Alexander M.P., Serdula M.K., Davis M. K., and Bowman, B.A., (2002). Assessment of infant feeding: the validity of measuring milk intake. *Nutr. Rev.* 60: 235-251
- Schoeller, D.A., van Santen E., Peterson D.W., Dietz W., Jaspan J., and Klein P.D., (1980). Total body water measurement in humans with ¹⁸O and ²H labeled water, *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 33 ;2686-2693.
- Victor O., 2015. Exclusive Breastfeeding can reduce Nigeria's burden of infants Mortality. Leadership Newspaper, January 12, 2015-
- Wells J.C. and Davies P.S., (1995). Correction for environmental water influx in measurement of milk volume intake by deuterium turnover in infants. *Early Hum.Dev.* 41, 177- 182.

- Westerterp K.R., Wouters L. and Van W.D., (1995). The Maastricht protocol for the measurement of body composition and energy expenditure with labeled water. *Obes Res; (suppl)* 3: 49–57.
- Whitehead R.G., Paul A.A., Black A.E. and Wiles S.J., (1981). Recommended Dietary Amounts of Energy for Pregnancy and Lactation in the United Kingdom. *Food and Nutrition Bulletin*.1981;(Supplement 5):259–265.
- WHO 2003. Global Strategy on Infant and young Child Feeding. World Health Organisation, UNICEF. ISBN: 9241562218. Available at <http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/42590/1/9241562218.pdf?ua=1&ua=1> (Accessed 11-11-2016).
- WHO 2008. Indicators for assessing infant and young child feeding practices : conclusions of a consensus meeting held 6–8 November 2007 in Washington D.C., USA. ISBN 978 92 4 159666 4. Available at http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/43895/1/9789241596664_eng.pdf (Accessed 11-11-2016)

Ojo J.O. et al. 2017. DETERMINATION OF INFANT MILK INTAKE AND MOTHER'S BODY COMPOSITION IN BREASTFEEDING MOTHERS FROM ILE-IFE, USING STABLE ISOTOPE TECHNIQUE

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